

Chemistry of alkoxo-bonded oxovanadium(V) complexes incorporating azophenolcarboxylates and ethylene glycol

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The reaction of $V^{IV}O(L)(H_2O)$ (where L = tridentate dinegative ONO donor azo ligands) with ethane-1,2-diol (H_2ed) in methanol solution produces the complex $V^VO(L)(Hed)$ (in which H_2ed coordinates in a monodeprotonated fashion) via aerial oxidation. The coordination sphere of the complexes is of the $VO(ONO)(OO)$ type, where O atoms are of oxo, phenolic, alcoholic and carboxylic and N is of azo type. The complexes are diamagnetic and exhibit only one ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) transition near 490 nm in addition to other two intra-ligand transitions around 410 and 330 nm. The complexes have low $V(V)/V(IV)$ reduction potentials in the region -0.40 V vs SCE leading to the stabilisation of pentavalent state.

Last two decades have witnessed tremendous development in the field of vanadium chemistry, particularly in its (IV/V) oxidation states because of their significant biochemical importance¹. Though oxovanadium alkoxides (viz. $V^VO(OR)$) are known for a long time², it is very recently that they are getting much importance because of their useful properties in the context of selective oxidation³, haloperoxidation⁴, phosphorylation⁵ and insulin mimicking⁶. Recently, a significant amount of work has been done by Chakravorty *et al.*⁷ and others⁸ in the mixed-ligand systems containing methanol/ethane-1,2-diol/propane-1,3-diol/glycerol with either *N*-salicylidene α -aminoacidate or hydrazones as co-ligands. However, to our knowledge, such type of complexes with ONO donor azo ligands and with aromatic carboxylate binding sites have not been reported so far. As a part of our programme on oxovanadium(IV/V) chemistry⁹, herein we report the results of such a study with azophenol-carboxylates (I) and ethane-1,2-diol (H_2ed). H_2ed behaves as a bidentate ligand and is coordinated to the vanadium in the monodeprotonated (Hed^-) form.

Results and Discussion

Two tridentate dinegative ONO donor azo ligands containing aromatic carboxylate group, H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 (general abbreviation H_2L) have been used in the present work with ethane-1,2-diol (H_2ed) as co-ligand. Upon treating the methanolic solution of $[V^{IV}O(L)(H_2O)]$ with excess H_2ed , the diamagnetic $[V^VO(L)(Hed)]$ complexes were formed via aerial oxidation. The reaction can be represented as

Though there is a probability of formation of alkoxy com-

pound with the solvent molecule but probably it is the chelate effect of H_2ed that predominates.

Despite our efforts none of the complexes provided crystals suitable for X-ray work. However, the meridional tridentate binding of $(L^1)^{2-}$ has been crystallographically well-documented¹⁰. The bidentate binding of Hed^- ion to oxovanadium(V) is also established⁷. On this basis, the most logical structure of the present family of complexes is that given by (II). The coordination of the weakly bonded OH group *trans* to the strongly bonded oxo group is the most logical.

IR and electronic spectra : Magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate that the complexes are diamagnetic and they display a strong $V=O$ stretch in the region $980\text{--}990$ cm^{-1} (Table 1) which is suggestive of hexacoordination⁷. The monodentate coordination nature of the carboxylate group is confirmed by the presence of one symmetric (~ 1340 cm^{-1}) and two asymmetric (~ 1640 and 1620 cm^{-1}) stretching modes^{7,11}. The appearance of a relatively broad band at

Table 1. Spectral data of the complexes

Compd.	λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	E_{pc} (V)
VO(L ¹)(Hed)	485 (1850), 410 (2100), 330 (6680)	-0.40
VO(L ²)(Hed)	495 (4430), 480 (4470), 410 ^a (1700), 320 (2200)	-0.40

^aShoulder.

3100–3200 cm^{-1} confirms the presence of bonded OH group of the Hed⁻ moiety and also suggests its involvement in hydrogen bonding probably with the uncoordinated carboxylate oxygen of a neighbouring molecule⁷. The characteristic N=N stretching mode is observed in the region 1380–1415 cm^{-1} . The band at 540–555 cm^{-1} is assigned to V–O (aryl) and those at 485–495 and 445–455 cm^{-1} to the V–N and V–O (carboxyl) bonds, respectively.

The dimethyl sulfoxide solution of d^0 [VO(L)(Hed)] complexes are orange-red in colour, exhibiting intense transitions. The one at the lowest energy is at around 490 nm, which is assigned to ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) excitation of the type $p \rightarrow d$, where p and d represent phenolate oxygen lone-pair and vanadium $3d$ orbitals respectively. Other two bands at around 410 and 330 nm are characteristic of N=N bond, due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions respectively.

Redox behaviour: In dimethyl sulfoxide solution, a one-electron cyclic voltammetric reduction peak occurs at around -0.40 V (vs saturated calomel electrode, SCE) due to metal reduction ($\text{VO}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{VO}^{2+}$). So, the lowering of the metal reduction potential due to ligation of Hed⁻ assists facile aerial oxidation of the metal site ($\text{VO}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{VO}^{3+}$). Other two reduction peaks, characteristic of the ligand, are also observed at high negative values, the one near -1.0 and other at around -1.3 V (vs SCE). These are due to the stepwise reduction of the azo (N=N) group.

Experimental

The complexes were synthesized using [$\text{V}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$] species¹². Electrochemical grade dimethyl sulfoxide and tetraethylammonium perchlorate were obtained as reported earlier¹³. All other chemicals and solvents (analytical grade) were used as supplied.

Electronic spectra (DMSO) were recorded with a Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer. Electrochemical measurements were performed on a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry sys-

tem according to the reported procedure¹⁴. All potentials reported are uncorrected for junction contributions. A Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyser was used to collect microanalytical data.

The reported two complexes were synthesized by the same general method.

(Ethane-1,2-diolato) (5-methyl azobenzene-2-olato-2'-carboxylato)oxovanadium(v), [VO(L¹)(Hed)]. General method: To a methanolic solution (30 cm^3) of [$\text{VO}(\text{L}^1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})$] (170 mg, 0.5 mmol) was added ethane-1,2-diol (1.11 g, 17.9 mmol; 1 cm^3). The mixture was refluxed for 1h, cooled (no precipitation) and the resulting deep pink-red solution was kept for slow evaporation at room temperature. The resulting reddish-brown solid was washed with distilled water and dried over (fused CaCl_2), 83%; yield for [$\text{VO}(\text{L}^2)(\text{Hed})$], 80%.

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Battacharya *et al.* : Chemistry of alkoxo-bonded oxovanadium(V) complexes incorporating azophenolcarboxylates *etc.*

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